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Barge maneuvering by a fleet of autonomous pushers

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Abstract

Contrasted to a single pusher boat maneuvering a barge, the use of multiple pusher boats may increase the maneuverability and consequently the safety of operation. This include maneuvering in narrow channels or regions with draft restrictions. This study presents the design and simulation of a barge-pushers system composed by six 0.5-ton pushers and a 17-ton barge. The barge is not self-propelled and the design control a group of six non-holonomic autonomous surface vessels serving as pusher boats, which maneuvers the barge to a desired location and orientation. The optimal control is obtained using a linear-quadratic regulator (LQR) and a linearized version of the system. Then, step responses of the linear and nonlinear models are compared and numerical simulations are performed using a three-dimensional robotic simulator with a nonlinear maneuvering model. The results showed that for this case, the nonlinear and the linear system dynamics had similar responses and the barge transportation process was accomplished successfully.

1. Introduction

Research and applications of autonomous boats have been increasing year by year, and the use of them to transport larger vessels is an important goal to be achieved.

Some authors have studied this floating structures transportation using articulated magnetic attachments (Esposito 2008) and steel wire ropes (Chen, Hopman, and Negenborn 2019). Here, a barge maneuvering performed by six pusher boats using only contact force is proposed, i.e., entrapping the barge and maneuvering.

To do that, a linearized model is used to optimize the control problem, which is simulated and compared to a nonlinear model. After that, a three-dimensional simulation is carried out with the software ROS (Robot Operating System) and Gazebo using a nonlinear maneuvering model.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 is dedicated for mathematical modeling of the nonlinear and linearized model. Also, the LQR

(Linear-Quadratic Regulator) optimum controller design technique is applied. In Section 3, results of the simulations are shown and discussed. The conclusion will be drawn in Section 4.

2. Methodology

This section aims to describe the various elements used in this study to achieve barge maneuvering using the pusher boats.

2.1. Barge

A rectangular not self-propelled barge was used, and its frame of reference and main physical parameters are shown in Figure 1 and Table 1 respectively.

Figure 1 – Barge frame of reference

Table 1 – Barge main characteristics

L (m)	9.4
B (m)	2.7
D (m)	1.3
T (m)	0.7
m (kg)	17800
I_{xx} ($kg \cdot m^2$)	13500
I_{yy} ($kg \cdot m^2$)	133700
I_{zz} ($kg \cdot m^2$)	141800

2.2. Pushers

One-meter-long non-holonomic autonomous surface vessels are used to push the barge. They have a cylindrical shape composed by three motors (main motor + two auxiliary, as shown in Figure 2) and their main characteristics are shown in Table 2.

Figure 2 – Pusher design

Table 2 - Pusher main characteristics

L (m)	1.0
B (m)	1.0
D (m)	1.4
T (m)	0.8
m (kg)	550
I_{xx} ($kg \cdot m^2$)	80
I_{yy} ($kg \cdot m^2$)	80
I_{zz} ($kg \cdot m^2$)	70

2.3. Control design

2.3.1. Pusher control

The pushers have two degrees of freedom, the first one is the rotation around its vertical centered axis and the second is to move forward. Each pusher i has the following control law to correct its course:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{\psi_i} &= \psi_{di} - \psi_i \\ F_{\psi_i Prop} &= K_{P\psi_i} e_{\psi_i} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where, e_{ψ_i} is the error between the desired yaw angle ψ_{di} and the actual yaw angle ψ_i of each individual i . $F_{\psi_i Prop}$ is the force applied to rotate the pusher and $K_{P\psi_i}$ is the proportional gain constant for the rotational motion.

2.3.2. Object transportation control

For the barge transportation, the desired forces and moments were also calculated based on a proportional controller, shown in Equation (2).

$$\begin{aligned} e_{x_T} &= x_{dT} - x_T \\ e_{y_T} &= y_{dT} - y_T \\ e_{\psi_T} &= \psi_{dT} - \psi_T \\ \mathcal{X} &= K_{Px_T} e_{x_T} + K_{P\dot{x}_T} \dot{x}_T \\ \mathcal{Y} &= K_{Py_T} e_{y_T} + K_{P\dot{y}_T} \dot{y}_T \\ \mathcal{N} &= K_{P\psi_T} e_{\psi_T} + K_{P\dot{\psi}_T} \dot{\psi}_T \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where, e_{x_T} , e_{y_T} and e_{ψ_T} are the error between the desired position and orientation of the barge ($x_{dT}, y_{dT}, \psi_{dT}$) and its actual position and orientation (x_T, y_T, ψ_T). The linear and angular velocities of the barge are given by $(\dot{x}_T, \dot{y}_T, \dot{\psi}_T)$, and each respective proportional gain constant is given by $(K_{Px_T}, K_{P\dot{x}_T}, K_{Py_T}, K_{P\dot{y}_T}, K_{P\psi_T}, K_{P\dot{\psi}_T})$.

2.3.3. Problem definition

Considering that the barge is entrapped by six pushers, which are assumed to be massless and applies the force normal to the contact surface. Also, an “equilibrium” state is expected to be achieved, i.e., the object is tightly held, as shown by Figure 3. Also, considering a 2D problem, there is the fixed-body reference frame $O_T X_T Y_T$ and the global reference frame OXY .

Figure 3 – Entrapped barge in “equilibrium” with six pushers (circles)

The barge position and orientation is (x_T, y_T, ψ_T) , which is located at the rectangle centroid. Each pusher has the position and orientation (x_i, y_i, ψ_i) , located at the circle centroid.

2.3.4. Nonlinear system dynamics

To move this barge-pushers system using the controller given by Equations (2), the system dynamics is obtained using the body-fixed reference frame shown in Figure 3 and Newton-Euler equations. Then, a simplified 3-DOF equations of motion can be represented as (Fossen 2011) in Equation (3).

$$\begin{aligned} m[\dot{u} - vr - x_G r^2 - y_G \dot{r}] &= \mathbf{X} \\ m[\dot{v} - ur - y_G r^2 + x_G \dot{r}] &= \mathbf{Y} \\ I_{ZZ} \dot{r} + m[x_G(\dot{v} + ur) - y_G(\dot{u} - vr)] &= \mathbf{N} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where u and v are linear velocities in X_T and Y_T directions and r is angular velocity around Z_T axes. Also, \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} are external forces and \mathbf{N} is external moment in $O_T X_T Y_T$ frame of reference, and are defined as follows:

$$\sum \mathbf{F}_{ext} = \mathbf{F}_D + \mathbf{F}_A + \mathbf{F}_P \quad (4)$$

Where $\sum \mathbf{F}_{ext}$ is the external forces and moments applied to the system, which are divided into damping terms \mathbf{F}_D , added mass terms \mathbf{F}_A and propulsion terms \mathbf{F}_P , discretized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}_D &= \mathbf{X}_{u|u} |u|u| \\ \mathbf{Y}_D &= \mathbf{Y}_{v|v} |v|v| \\ \mathbf{N}_D &= \mathbf{N}_{r|r} |r|r| \\ \mathbf{X}_A &= \mathbf{X}_{\dot{u}} \dot{u} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}_A &= \mathbf{Y}_{\dot{v}} \dot{v} \\ \mathbf{N}_A &= \mathbf{N}_{\dot{r}} \dot{r} \\ \mathbf{X}_P &= \mathcal{X} \\ \mathbf{Y}_P &= \mathcal{Y} \\ \mathbf{N}_P &= \mathcal{N} \end{aligned}$$

2.3.5. Linearized system dynamics

To optimize the controller using a Linear-Quadratic Regulator (LQR) technique, the damping terms from Equations (5) were linearized around specific velocities $(\dot{u}, \dot{v}, \dot{r})$, as shown in Equations (6).

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{X}}_D &\approx \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{X}_D}{\partial u} \right|_{\dot{u}} u = \hat{\mathbf{X}}_u u \\ \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_D &\approx \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{Y}_D}{\partial v} \right|_{\dot{v}} v = \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_v v \\ \hat{\mathbf{N}}_D &\approx \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{N}_D}{\partial r} \right|_{\dot{r}} r = \hat{\mathbf{N}}_r r \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

2.3.6. State space representation

Written the system into a state space form with variables $x_1 = x$, $x_2 = \dot{x}$, $x_3 = y$, $x_4 = \dot{y}$, $x_5 = \psi$ and $x_6 = r$, also, considering $x_G = y_G = 0$ and $vr = ur \approx 0$, the system becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} m\dot{x}_2 &= \hat{\mathbf{X}}_u x_2 + \mathbf{X}_{\dot{u}} \dot{x}_2 + \mathcal{X} \\ m\dot{x}_4 &= \hat{\mathbf{Y}}_v x_4 + \mathbf{Y}_{\dot{v}} \dot{x}_4 + \mathcal{Y} \\ I_{ZZ} \dot{x}_6 &= \hat{\mathbf{N}}_r x_6 + \mathbf{N}_{\dot{r}} \dot{x}_6 + \mathcal{N} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Then, to obtain a first-order linear system:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= x_2 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= (\hat{\mathbf{X}}_u x_2 + \mathcal{X}) / (m - \mathbf{X}_{\dot{u}}) \\ \dot{x}_3 &= x_4 \\ \dot{x}_4 &= (\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_v x_4 + \mathcal{Y}) / (m - \mathbf{Y}_{\dot{v}}) \\ \dot{x}_5 &= x_6 \\ \dot{x}_6 &= (\hat{\mathbf{N}}_r x_6 + \mathcal{N}) / (I_{ZZ} - \mathbf{N}_{\dot{r}}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the system can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}_n &= [\mathbf{A}][\mathbf{x}_n] + [\mathbf{B}][\mathbf{u}] \\ \mathbf{y}_n &= [\mathbf{C}][\mathbf{x}_n] + [\mathbf{D}][\mathbf{u}] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Where, $[\mathbf{x}_n]$ is the state vector, $[\mathbf{y}_n]$ the output vector, $[\mathbf{u}]$ the input vector, $[\mathbf{A}]$ the system matrix, $[\mathbf{B}]$ the input matrix, $[\mathbf{C}]$ the output matrix and $[\mathbf{D}]$ the feedforward matrix.

2.3.7. Closed-loop system

3. Figure 4 - Schematic for the closed-loop system

Developing the system shown in Equations (9) with a proportional controller where $\mathbf{u} = -K_P \mathbf{x}_n$ and considering that $\mathbf{y}_n = \mathbf{x}_n$, the closed-loop system shown in Figure 4 becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{[x_n]} &= [A][x_n] + [B][u] \\ [x_n] &= ([A] - [B][K_P])[x_n] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

To estimate the feedback gains of this system the LQR technique based on (Kwakernaak and Sivan 1972) is used:

$$J(\mathbf{u}) = \int_0^{\infty} (\mathbf{x}^T Q \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{u}^T R \mathbf{u}) dt \quad (11)$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= I_6 \\ R &= 0.01I_3 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The data used for this step is shown in Table 3, which was linearized around $\dot{u} = \dot{v} = \dot{r} = 0.017 [m/s, m/s, rad/s]$.

Using the software MATLAB the nonlinear and the linearized models response were simulated for a step with $x_T = 1m$, $y_T = 1m$ and $\psi_T = 10deg$, using the gains constants from Table 4. These gains were obtained considering a 1200s finished maneuver.

Table 3 - Barge-pushers system data

$\mathbf{X}_{u u}$	-1890	$\mathbf{N}_{\dot{r}}$	-110000
$\mathbf{Y}_{v v}$	-11750	$\hat{\mathbf{X}}_u$	-63
$\mathbf{N}_{r r}$	-3840	$\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_v$	-392
$\mathbf{X}_{\dot{u}}$	-6900	$\hat{\mathbf{N}}_r$	-128
$\mathbf{Y}_{\dot{v}}$	-16500		

The proportional gain constants obtained for this system are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 – Gains constants obtained using LQR

K_{Px_T}	10	K_{Py_T}	524
K_{Px_T}	643	$K_{P\psi_T}$	10
K_{Py_T}	10	K_{Pr_T}	2120

2.3.8. Thrust allocation

Forces and moments required by the control system are distributed using a thrust-allocation algorithm proposed by (Sørdalen 1997), for details see (de Andrade 2020). For the present case, each pusher is treated as a thruster, then:

$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{T} = \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{T} = [F_{Transp_i}]^T, i = 1, \dots, 6 \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{s}_i & \dots \\ \mathbf{c}_i & \dots \\ -\mathbf{c}_i y_i + \mathbf{s}_i x_i & \dots \end{bmatrix}, i = 1, \dots, 6 \quad (15)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = [\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{N}]^T \quad (16)$$

Where $\mathbf{c}_i = \cos(\psi_i)$, $\mathbf{s}_i = \sin(\psi_i)$, \mathbf{A} is a matrix that depends on the pushers' positions (x_i, y_i) and orientations ψ_i . The force exerted by the pushers are represented by \mathbf{T} and the forces of surge, sway and the moment in the yaw direction are denoted by $\boldsymbol{\tau}$.

2.4 Method

To perform the barge transportation, numerical simulations are carried out. The pushers' system is homogeneous with direct communication and centralized control architecture. The navigation of the barge-pushers system is accomplished by using optimal control theory, as shown in Subsection 2.3.

Figure 5 - Flowchart of the process followed by the system for each time step

The stages for this transportation are shown in Figure 5, being the following:

- A. Position and orientation of the barge is obtained;
- B. Pushers' position variations are calculated;
- C. If **B** is below ε , then transportation is triggered with a constant $F_{PropMax}$ plus a variable F_{Transp} ;
- D. If **B** is above ε , there is no transportation, only navigation with a constant F_{Prop} .

The value of Δt and ε are free choices (for this study, $\Delta t = 3s$ and $\varepsilon = 1\%$). Also, the proposed propulsion force has two levels: F_{Prop} for entrapping and $F_{PropMax}$ for transportation, with $F_{PropMax} > F_{Prop} > 0$ and $F_{Transp} < F_{PropMax}$, this last guarantees the push-only function for each boat.

2.4.1 Numerical simulations

ROS (Robot Operating System) and Gazebo is used to simulate the complete system, as can be observed in Figure 6. The nonlinear maneuvering model was based on (Bingham 2018).

Figure 6 - Three-dimensional simulator. The red object is the barge and the yellow ones are the pushers

The main objective here is to maneuver the barge from $(x = 0, y = 0, \psi = 0)$ to $(x = 5, y = 5, \psi = 0)$ using the proposed method shown in Figure 5.

3 Results and Discussion

3.4.1 Nonlinear vs linearized response

The step responses for the nonlinear and linearized models can be observed in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - Step response of the nonlinear and linearized models

As expected, before 1200s the oscillations have been finished and there are no expressive differences between both models. Then, for this case, this validate the use of the linearized model to obtain the gain constants using the LQR design technique.

3.4.2 Barge transportation

The result of the simulation using ROS and Gazebo can be observed in Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Barge transportation from $(x=0, y=0, \psi=0)$ to $(x=5, y=5, \psi=0)$. The blue cross is the initial point of the barge (gray rectangle), and the red cross is the final objective point. Each pusher (circles) is identified by a unique color and its trajectories can also be observed.

Some small perturbations may be observed in the trajectory of the pushers. This fact can be due to the

collision effect simulated by the software Gazebo, which simulate the collision between the objects using its physics engine.

Also, it is possible to notice that the arrangement did not change expressively due to the $F_{Transp} < F_{PropMax}$ condition and the absence of external environmental perturbations. Moreover, the shape of the responses was similar to that one's obtained for the step responses.

4 Conclusions

The paper addresses the problem of a barge maneuvering by six autonomous pusher boats.

The simulations have suggested that the transportation without the use of extra mechanisms can be achieved only through the contact force. No need to use articulated magnetic attachments or wire ropes. Moreover, for this case, the linear model was sufficient to optimize the controller problem using the LQR design technique.

However, it is important to say that further experimental model tests need to be carried out to validate these achievements. Also, the introduction of environmental perturbations is necessary to observe the system robustness.

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